

Exploring the Coverage of the Scientific Production of the University of Bologna within OpenCitations

Erica Andreose ¹

¹University of Bologna

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the coverage of publications available in the CRIS (Current Research Information System) infrastructure of the University of Bologna and implemented in the IRIS platform, within the databases of OpenCitations. Specifically, we quantify the proportion of IRIS publications included in OpenCitations Meta, examine the types of publications best covered, evaluate the number of citations within OpenCitations Index involving IRIS publications as either citing or cited entities, and the extent to which these citations reference works outside of IRIS. Our methodology filters and transforms data dumps of IRIS and OpenCitations, creating novel datasets that we use to gather the answers to the research questions. Our findings reveal that only 37.7% of IRIS is covered in OpenCitations Meta, with journal articles exhibiting the highest coverage. We identified 7,723,941 citations in OpenCitations Index involving IRIS-related publications, with 3,989,540 coming from non-IRIS sources, and 3,441,830 pointing to publications outside IRIS. Only 353,414 citations involved both citing and cited publications from IRIS. These findings highlight deficiencies and discrepancies, mainly related to duplicate entries in both the IRIS system and the OpenCitations corpora. Our research output could aid in identifying and correcting these issues, and also providing a baseline for the sharing of missing valuable data across the two infrastructures which would enhance the overall effectiveness and accuracy of both infrastructures.

Keywords: Scientometrics, informetrics, Bibliographic collection, OpenCitations.

1. Introduction

The rise of platforms adhering to Open Science principles has significantly enhanced the accessibility, availability, and reuse of scientific knowledge, providing a strong alternative to commercial sources of scholarly information. According to UNESCO, Open Science is

an inclusive concept that combines various movements and practices aimed at making scientific knowledge openly available to all, promoting scientific collaboration, and involving societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community in the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation, and communication (UNESCO, 2021). The Open Science movement is characterized by four phases: Open source software, Open Access publications of scientific articles, Open research data sets, and Open bibliographic metadata (Peroni & Shotton, 2020). One platform that follows the principles and the phases of this movement, developed at the University of Bologna, is IRIS, the implementation of the Current Research Information System (CRIS)¹ that facilitates the management and dissemination of research products exclusively authored by the personnel of the University of Bologna. IRIS allows researchers to publish their work, making it freely accessible to users. This paper focuses on IRIS, examining its coverage within OpenCitations Meta and analyzing citation patterns involving IRIS publications. OpenCitations² (Peroni & Shotton, 2020) is an independent organization for open scholarship that publishes open bibliographic resources (BRs) and citation data using Semantic Web technologies, storing and managing this information in their Corpora. It advocates for open citations and is managed by the Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata at the University of Bologna. OpenCitations adheres to the founding principles of Open Science, FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), ensuring that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, and to the I4OC³ recommendations for structured, separable, and open citation data.

Previous attempts at mapping entities between large open bibliographic metadata collections have been made in the past. Spinaci et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive study to measure the coverage of Digital Humanities publications across various bibliographic data sources, including both open and proprietary databases. Rizzetto & Peroni (2023) developed a methodology for mapping entities between OpenCitations Meta and OpenAlex, with the goal of integrating identifiers and interlinking these datasets.

This study focuses on IRIS, and it aims to explore the extent to which the University of Bologna’s research outputs, as recorded in the IRIS system, are represented within the OpenCitations infrastructure. By analyzing the coverage of publications and their citations, this study aims to shed light on the visibility and interconnectedness of academic work across open-access platforms as OpenCitations. The main research questions addressed in the study are:

1. What is the coverage of the publications available in IRIS (strictly concerning research conducted within the University of Bologna) in OpenCitations Meta?
2. What are the types of publications that are better covered in the portion of OpenCitations Meta covered by IRIS?

¹<https://cris.unibo.it/>

²<https://opencitations.net/>

³<https://i4oc.org/>

3. What is the amount of citations (according to OpenCitations Index) coming from the IRIS publications that is involved in OpenCitations Meta (as citing entity and as cited entity)?
4. How many of these citations come from and go to publications that are not included in IRIS?
5. How many of these citations involve publications in IRIS as both citing and cited entities?

The software developed for this study is available on GitHub⁴ and a descriptive version of the methodology presented has been published on Protocols.io⁵.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Data

The data used for this research were collected from publicly available data dumps provided by the administrators of the relevant research objects.

The IRIS data dump⁶, provided by researchers from the University of Bologna and hosted on the university's AMSActa repository, contains the bibliographic metadata of publications of the scholars of the university. This information was extracted from the IRIS platform, which implements the Current Research Information System (CRIS) at the University of Bologna. The specific version used for this study, dated June 04, 2024, consists of seven distinct CSV files, each descriptive of a specific aspect of the publications. The dataset contains 304,983 bibliographic entities and has a total size of 267 MB. The dataset comprises eight CSV files that provide a rich set of metadata about academic publications. It includes details about the individuals involved, such as authors and editors, as well as publication identifiers like DOIs. Additionally, the dataset captures information on the language of the publications, basic bibliographic details like titles, publication dates, and types, along with publisher information. Further contextual metadata is provided, detailing aspects such as publication venues and editorial roles. A README file accompanies the dataset, offering additional documentation and guidance.

For OpenCitations data, we deliberately chose data dumps provided by the organization rather than querying SPARQL endpoints of the Meta and Index services to ensure the reproducibility of our research. OpenCitations Meta (Massari et al., 2024) is a complementary database to OpenCitations, managing metadata of citing and cited academic publications. It uses a provenance model based on the PROV Ontology (W3C standard),

⁴<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

⁵Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024e). Exploring the coverage of the scientific production of the university of bologna in opencitations. *protocols.io*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.3byl497wjgo5/v5>

⁶Amurri, A., Giachino, E., & Peroni, S. (2024, June). Unibo iris bibliographic data dump, dated 4 june 2024. <https://amsacta.unibo.it/id/eprint/7736/>

ensuring transparency and traceability by capturing details about data creation, modification, and primary sources. Provenance data is stored in the Resource Description Framework (RDF), integrating with semantic web technologies.

The OpenCitations Meta dump⁷ contains bibliographic metadata in CSV format for entities in OpenCitations Index, each identified by a unique OMID (OpenCitations Meta Identifier). The OMID format is:

br/0601

where "br" is for “bibliographic resource”, "060" is the supplier prefix (OpenCitations Meta) and "1" is the sequential number. The April 2024 version includes 114,703,611 entities, compressed into 11 GB (46 GB unzipped, spread across 28,249 files), with each line providing key metadata like author names, publication dates, and identifiers. Each line in the CSV files represents a bibliographic resource and includes several key fields. These fields provide information such as the document’s unique ID, title, authors, publication date, and the venue to which the document belongs. Additionally, details about the volume, issue, and page range are recorded, along with the type of resource, the publisher, and any editors involved. This structured metadata allows for a comprehensive description of each bibliographic entry.

OpenCitations Index (Heibi et al., 2024) is a citation index built on the bibliographic metadata stored in OpenCitations Meta and managed by OpenCitations. It hosts citation data submitted by third parties, such as authors and scholars, making this data openly available. Citations are treated as first-class data entities, allowing for properties like the date of creation, time span, and type. Rather than storing metadata about the citing and cited publications, the index retrieves bibliographic information via unique identifiers through an API.

The OpenCitations Index dump⁸ contains citation data in CSV format, with each citation assigned a unique OCI (OpenCitations Identifier), formatted as:

oci:06101801781-062501777134

This represents the citing and cited publication (Peroni & Shotton, 2020). The November 2023 version contains 1,975,552,846 citations and 89,920,081 bibliographic resources, weighing 26.8 GB when zipped (171 GB unzipped). Each line in the CSV file represents a citation and contains several important fields. These include the Open Citation Identifier (OCI) for the citation, the OMID identifiers of both the citing and cited entities, and the citation’s creation date, which corresponds to the publication date of the citing entity. Additionally, the file records the time span between the publication dates of the citing and cited entities. It also indicates whether the citation is a journal self-citation (where both

⁷OpenCitations. (2022, December). Opencitations meta csv dataset of all bibliographic metadata. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21747461.v8>

⁸OpenCitations. (2023, October). Opencitations index csv dataset of all the citation data. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24356626.v2>

entities are published in the same journal) or an author self-citation (where the entities share at least one author).

2.2 Methods

The workflow starts with the extraction of a list of unique identifiers from the IRIS dump, which we use to search for BRs within OC Meta. Specifically, we extract all entities in IRIS with DOI, ISBN, or PMID identifiers. Of the 304,983 entities in the IRIS dump, we found 201,471 with at least one of these PID. From this filtering process we create the first of our novel datasets, *Iris No ID*⁹, containing the metadata of 103,481 IRIS entities without a DOI, ISBN, or PMID. This dataset integrates information from various IRIS tables, possibly helping to trace these entities in future integration into Meta. The remaining 201,471 entries with at least one of the PIDs supported in OC Meta are used to build the list of unique identifiers. We select for each BR one of the three PIDs, giving priority to DOIs, then PMIDs and lastly ISBNs in cases in which one entry has more than one, along with the IRIS internal ID and 'type' label. Malformed identifiers are sanitized and invalid ones discarded, and all identifiers are unified in format and converted to lowercase for consistency with the Meta dataset. Table 1 summarizes the number of identifiers before and after the filtering process.

PID Type	Initial count	Invalid count	Final count
DOI	131,048	123	130,925
ISBN	81,526	831	67,850
PMID	45,855	4	1,861
Total	258,429	958	200,636

Table 1: Number of entities with DOI, ISBN, and PMID before and after the filtering process.

2.2.1 Deduplication

Next, the list undergoes a process of deduplication to remove the 42,720 cases in which we found the same PID to be associated to multiple IRIS entries. To address these instances we act on DOIs, ISBNs and PMIDs separately, establishing a priority system that ranks the duplicated BRs based on their type and allows us to pick the preferred one. This system, implemented in the form of preference Dataframes described in the tables below, has been devised following the manual investigation of sample duplicate records, which led to the discovery that only five types ensures that the final dataset includes only the most relevant and accurate entries filtered between DOIs and ISBNs. For what concerns the PMIDs we exclude the duplicate case type "Abstracts" and keep only the first occurrence

⁹Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024c, May). Iris No ID. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897759.v2>

of each "Article". The cases addressed with these priority Dataframes mostly involved examples of multiple entries referring to the insertion of the same PID for both content and container. A more detailed analysis of this issue can be found in section 3.4.

Meta Type	Iris type	Preference
Journal articles	35 - 1.01 Articolo in rivista	0
Book	50 - 3.02 Curatela	1
Book chapters	41 - 2.01 Capitolo / saggio in libro	2
Proceedings article	57 - 4.01 Contributo in Atti di convegno	3

Table 2: DOI Priority dataframe. A lower preference has higher priority.

Meta Type	Iris type	Preference
Book	49 - 3.01 Monografia	0
Book	35 - 1.01 Articolo in rivista	1

Table 3: ISBN Priority dataframe. A lower preference has higher priority.

After this process, we arrive at a list of 169,687 unique PIDs, reduced from the original 258,429 entities. We use this list to filter the OC Meta data dump in order to create the first of two main output datasets that we use to answer the research questions of the study: *Iris in Meta*¹⁰ (IIM). This dataset contains all BRs from OC Meta that are associated with DOI, PMID or ISBN from the list of unique PIDs extracted from IRIS.

After extracting the data from the Meta dump, this dataset also undergoes a deduplication process to remove duplicates deriving from an error in OC Meta where the same BR appears multiple times with different OMIDs. Our analysis identified 2,121 unique entries in the IIM dataset affected by this issue (each appearing two or more times). To resolve these duplicates, we keep the first occurrence when the entities share the same type. If the entities have different types, we first exclude those with empty types and then select the preferred entity based on a priority list according to the entity type.

Meta Type	Iris type	Preference
Journal articles	35 - 1.01 Articolo in rivista	0
Book chapters	41 - 2.01 Capitolo / saggio in libro	1
Book chapters	42 - 2.02 Prefazione	2

Table 4: Priority dataframe for IIM filtering. A lower preference has higher priority.

Complementary to IIM, the *Iris Not in Meta*¹¹ (INIM) dataset is also created, containing all the BRs from the IRIS dump that have a DOI, ISBN or PMID but that have

¹⁰Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024b, May). *Iris in Meta*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v2>

¹¹Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024d, May). *Iris Not In Meta*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v2>

not been found in OC Meta.

The second part of our research focuses on the coverage of IRIS in OpenCitations Index. In order to answer the research questions related to this issue, we generate the *Iris in Index*¹² (III) dataset by extracting all the OMIDs from the *Iris in Meta* dataset and filtering the OC Index dump to retrieve all citations in which an OMID from the list appears as either 'cited' or as 'citing' entity.

With these datasets at our disposal, the final phase of our research involved querying them to answer the research questions.

3. Results

The length of the final *Iris in Meta* dataset amounts to 115,083 entities, representing 67.8% of the list of deduplicated PIDs extracted from IRIS and 37.7% of the whole unfiltered IRIS dump. The best covered type of publications, in relation to the amount of publications present for each type in the list of PIDs used for the search, are journal articles, followed by replicas, BRs without a type and contributions in conference proceedings. The breakdown of publication types in IRIS and in *Iris in Meta* is shown in the following table:

Analyzing this *Iris In Index* dataset, we found that 7,723,941 citations in OC Index involve a BR present in IRIS as either citing or cited entity. Of these, 3,433,845 cite publications that are not included in IRIS and 3,936,674 are cited by publications that are not included in IRIS. Additionally 353,422 citations involve publications included in IRIS as both citing and cited entity.

3.1 Comparative analysis of the types

Comparing the types of the BRs as described in IRIS and Meta also reveals some interesting insights on the extent to which the types align between the two infrastructures. To achieve this, we analyzed the types of IRIS¹³ present within our data dump and the corresponding Meta types resulting from the data alignment. We created a pair-wise mapping of the typologies (shown in appendix A) and checked the amount of entries that respected it. The empty Meta value ("") was interpreted as "No type" during the alignment process. The result of this analysis shows that the vast majority of the entities (108,036) have a coherent type between the two datasets, while the remaining 7,047 entities have a different type in the two datasets.

¹²Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024a, May). *Iris in Index*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879441.v2>

¹³<https://iris.inrim.it/community-list>

IRIS type	IRIS count	IIM count	%
1.01 Articolo in rivista	111502	100493	90.13
1.04 Replica / breve intervento (e simili)	1821	1438	78.97
null	9	6	66.67
4.01 Contributo in Atti di convegno	16732	8064	48.20
1.06 Abstract in rivista	887	310	34.95
1.02 Nota a sentenza	71	19	26.76
7.05 Banche dati	53	14	26.42
1.03 Recensione in rivista	987	254	25.73
7.15 Test psicologici	8	2	25.00
5.03 Contributo in rivista (Traduzione)	45	11	24.44
4.03 Poster	224	44	19.64
7.13 Rapporto tecnico	114	21	18.42
2.05 Voce in dizionario o enciclopedia	745	134	17.99
2.01 Capitolo / saggio in libro	22746	3645	16.02
4.02 Riassunto (Abstract)	1174	142	12.10
1.05 Scheda bibliografica	29	2	6.90
3.02 Curatela	2805	192	6.84
2.02 Prefazione	593	36	6.07
3.01 Monografia / trattato scientifico in forma di libro	6593	221	3.35
2.08 Recensione in volume	33	1	3.03
2.06 Commento giuridico	197	5	2.54
2.04 Breve introduzione	866	20	2.31
3.07 Bibliografia	46	1	2.17
3.04 Pubblicazione di fonti inedite	46	1	2.17
5.02 Contributo in volume (Traduzione)	167	2	1.20
3.03 Edizione critica	322	3	0.93
2.03 Postfazione	143	1	0.70
5.01 Libro (Traduzione)	489	1	0.20

Table 5: Number of the IRIS types as found in IRIS and IIM, sorted by percentage.

3.2 Entities with no PID

Analyzing the *Iris No ID* dataset, we found that 33.9% of the BRs in the IRIS data dump do not have any of the type of PIDs that OC Meta collects in their databases. This makes the searching of these entities within OC Meta or other databases practically impossible without a prior search for identifiers in other, broader, infrastructures. During the preliminary phases of the research, an attempt was made to leverage the Crossref¹⁴ API to search for these entities by their additional metadata present in IRIS, such as the title, authors and publisher. We found this approach to be functional at retrieving quite a good percentage of the entities without PIDs, but also painfully slow and unfortunately hindered by the rate limits of the API that made searching for the whole lot impossible for our time constraints.

¹⁴<https://www.crossref.org/>

Figure 1: Overview of the mismatching types between IRIS and Meta

Category	Count
Entities with a DOI, ISBN, or PMID	201,471
Entities without a DOI, ISBN, or PMID	103,481
Total Entities	304,952

Table 6: Entities with and without a PID (DOI, ISBN, or PMID) in the dataset.

IRIS type	count
1.01 Articolo in rivista	37670
4.02 Riassunto (Abstract)	16356
4.01 Contributo in Atti di convegno	13267
2.01 Capitolo / saggio in libro	6666
1.03 Recensione in rivista	5343

Table 7: Overview of the top 5 types of BR in the INOID dataset.

3.3 Non-mapped analysis

From the analysis of the *Iris Not in Meta* dataset we discovered that 32.1% of the PIDs stored in the list created from IRIS and searched within OC Meta did not find a match. The vast majority of this portion of BRs are identified by ISBNs.

PID type	Count
ISBN	37,763
DOI	15,915
PMID	926
total	54,604

Table 8: Count of PIDs of the entities not found in Meta by type.

IRIS type	count
2.01 Capitolo / saggio in libro	19102
1.01 Articolo in rivista	11009
4.01 Contributo in Atti di convegno	8647
3.01 Monografia / trattato scientifico in forma di libro	6372
3.02 Curatela	2692

Table 9: Overview of the top 5 types of the IRIS BRs not present in OC Meta.

3.4 Duplicates analysis

As mentioned in the "Methods" section, during the extraction of the list of identifiers from IRIS, we identified cases where IRIS entries were associated with more than one PID. Specifically, 50,500 duplicates were found, involving 42,720 unique external IDs linked to multiple IRIS entries. In some cases, the same PID was associated with up to 275 different IRIS entries. This issue is particularly prevalent with ISBNs, as most duplications stem from incorrect aggregation of content and container identifiers. It is common in IRIS to find entries for distinct items sharing the same PID, where the PID does not specifically refer to any of the individual items but rather to the larger container that holds them. A clear example of this issue is the case of the 275 IRIS entries, which represent a series of individual entries from the Dizionario Bibliografico degli Italiani, all linked to the same ISBN for the volume of the dictionary in which they are contained. This pattern is frequently observed in similar cases involving dictionary or encyclopedia entries, as well as book chapters, proceedings articles, and journal articles.

The study and analysis of these groupings of identical PIDs led to the development of the priority list shown in Table 4. This list follows a specific order based on a heuristic developed from manual examination of the case studies and their final standardization. The most recurrent pattern observed was content being recorded with the PID of the container. However, the reverse was also encountered in some specific cases, which is why the priority list includes entries for Journal Articles and Proceedings Articles as well.

duplicate PID type	Count
ISBN	10,933
DOI	832
PMID	6
total	19,771

Table 10: Count of duplicate PIDs by type.

4. Discussion and Limitations

The results highlight how the University of Bologna’s research, captured through the Iris platform, is well-represented and influential both within and beyond the academic community. The significant overlap between Iris and OpenCitations Meta demonstrates that the university’s research output is well-aligned with broader scholarly communication networks, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of its academic contributions. The distribution of the entity types is also consistent with expectations. A large portion of citations to Iris publications comes from external sources reflecting the relevance and outreach of the university’s research, signaling its integration into the wider academic landscape. At the same time, the strong internal citation network within the Iris in Index dataset, where publications cite and are cited by other Iris entities, shows a collaborative internal academic environment. The balance between external and internal citations suggests that while the university is actively engaged with global research efforts, it also maintains a robust internal exchange of knowledge.

One of the main challenges of the study was the incomplete nature of the IRIS dataset. Of the 304,983 entities, only 201,471 had a DOI, ISBN, or PMID, leaving a significant number without identifiers that are crucial for integrating with external databases like OpenCitations Meta and Index. To handle this, a separate "Iris No Id" dataset was created for these entries, but their lack of identifiers made it difficult to fully trace their impact and citation relationships. Another limitation arose from the classification differences between Iris and OpenCitations Meta. While most entities (108,036) had matching types across both datasets, 7,047 entities exhibited discrepancies, suggesting inconsistencies in the classification systems used by the two datasets. These mismatches could impact the precision of our analysis, especially in comparing publication types and citation relationships. For a more accurate mapping of the types, it would be advisable to refer to OpenCitations Meta documentation¹⁵ for the complete and updated list of Meta types (which includes more labels than those we have used), to be cross-checked with the full list of IRIS types. Additionally, the OpenCitations Meta dataset contained some duplicates, where bibliographic entities appeared multiple times under different OMID identifiers. Although filtering was applied to remove these duplicates, residual data quality issues

¹⁵https://github.com/opencitations/metadata/blob/master/documentation/csv_documentation-v1_1_0.pdf

may still affect the accuracy of our findings, potentially leading to inflated citation counts or misinterpretations of the relationships between publications.

5. Conclusions

Our research provides a comprehensive overview of the representation and citation dynamics of IRIS publications within the OpenCitations Meta and Index databases. By analyzing the types of publications, the degree of coherence between the entity types in the iris and Meta datasets, the extent of citation involvement, and the interaction between IRIS-affiliated publications and external works, we have garnered valuable insights that can guide future research and policy decisions.

Understanding the alignment between institutional repositories like IRIS and open bibliographic databases is crucial for improving the accessibility, transparency, and dissemination of research. This type of investigation helps identify gaps and opportunities for enhancing the sharing of scholarly data, ultimately contributing to a more open and interconnected research ecosystem. Moreover, it underscores the importance of accurate and comprehensive bibliographic data for advancing open access initiatives and supporting better-informed research practices globally.

Overall, we emphasize the importance of enhancing the visibility and traceability of IRIS publications, and having a strong alignment in classification schemes. By addressing the identified gaps and fostering a more inclusive representation in citation databases, academic institutions can better assess and amplify the impact of their research. Additionally, the observed citation patterns provide insights into potential areas for collaboration and interdisciplinary research, paving the way for future academic and policy developments.

References

- Amurri, A., Giachino, E., & Peroni, S. (2024, June). Unibo iris bibliographic data dump, dated 4 june 2024. <https://amsacta.unibo.it/id/eprint/7736/>
- Heibi, I., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., & Soricetti, M. (2024). The opencitations index. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.02321>
- Massari, A., Mariani, F., Heibi, I., Peroni, S., & Shotton, D. (2024). Opencitations meta. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1–26. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292
- OpenCitations. (2022, December). Opencitations meta csv dataset of all bibliographic metadata. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21747461.v8>
- OpenCitations. (2023, October). Opencitations index csv dataset of all the citation data. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24356626.v2>
- Peroni, S., & Shotton, D. (2020). Opencitations, an infrastructure organization for open scholarship. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 428–444. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00023

- Rizzetto, E., & Peroni, S. (2023). Mapping bibliographic metadata collections: The case of opencitations meta and openalex. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.16523>
- Spinaci, G., Colavizza, G., & Peroni, S. (2022). A map of Digital Humanities research across bibliographic data sources. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 37(4), 1254–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/fqac016>
- UNESCO. (2021). Unesco recommendation on open science. <https://doi.org/10.54677/mnmh8546>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., et al. (2016). The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024a, May). Iris in Index. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879441.v2>
- Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024b, May). Iris in Meta. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v2>
- Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024c, May). Iris No ID. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897759.v2>
- Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024d, May). *Iris Not In Meta*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v2>
- Zilli, L., Andreose, E., & di Marzo, S. (2024e). Exploring the coverage of the scientific production of the university of bologna in opencitations. *protocols.io*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.3byl497wjgo5/v5>

A. IRIS-OCMeta type mapping

IRIS type	Meta type
7.05 Banche dati 7.15 Test psicologici	dataset
1.04 Replica / breve intervento (e simili) 2.04 Breve introduzione 2.02 Prefazione 2.03 Postfazione 4.02 Riassunto (Abstract) 4.03 Poster 1.02 Nota a sentenza 2.06 Commento giuridico 3.04 Pubblicazione di fonti inedite	other
2.05 Voce in dizionario o enciclopedia 1.05 Scheda bibliografica	reference entry
4.01 Contributo in Atti di convegno	proceedings article
7.13 Rapporto tecnico	report
2.01 Capitolo / saggio in libro 2.08 Recensione in volume 5.02 Contributo in volume (Traduzione)	book chapter
3.01 Monografia / trattato scientifico in forma di libro 5.01 Libro (Traduzione) 3.02 Curatela 3.03 Edizione critica	book
1.01 Articolo in rivista 5.03 Contributo in rivista (Traduzione) 1.06 Abstract in rivista 1.03 Recensione in rivista	journal article
3.07 Bibliografia	reference book
None	" "

Table 11: Mapping of the types from IRIS and OpenCitations Meta.